

Development of a Learning Management System (LMS) Based on Moodle on the Problem-Based Learning Model (Hydrocarbon Basic Material)

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Abstract:

This research aims to: (1) produce a Moodle-based LMS product that is feasible in improving learning outcomes using the *Problem-Based Learning* model for hydrocarbon material for SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung (2) find out the practical and effective Moodle-based *Media Learning Management System* (LMS) on the *Problem Model Based Learning* on hydrocarbon material. This type of research is R & D or research and development using the ADDIE model, namely: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The subjects of this research were students in class XI MIA 3 SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung. The data collection techniques used were

interviews, questionnaires, and tests. The results of this research are as follows. (1) LMS products developed with the Moodle application (2) Moodle-based LMS products have met the criteria and been declared suitable as learning media based on media expert validation with a score of 3.33 with the criteria "Very Valid", based on material expert validation with an average score of 3.72 with the criterion "Very valid", and based on teacher and student user responses with a percentage of 92.5% and 85% with the criterion "Very Practical". (3) The learning outcomes of class XI MIA 3 SMA Negeri 1 Tinambung improved after using Moodle-based LMS. The effectiveness of the product for Moodle-based LMS is proven by increasing learning outcomes which is known from the percentage of learning outcomes, namely 85.29%.

Keywords: Moodle-based LMS, Problem-Based Learning, ADDIE Model, Learning Outcomes.

Introduction

The influence of developments in information and communication technology knowledge has led to changes in infrastructure or networks which have given rise to network-based learning and with advances in the development of hardware and software this has given rise to very

significant influences such as e-learning-based learning (Arya, 2017).

Based on the results of initial observations at SMAN 1 Tinambung, information, and data were obtained that there was still a lack of utilization of existing technology, where the school was facilitated by a Wi-Fi network and all

students already had cellphones and were allowed to use them during the learning process. There are several obstacles for educators, where one of the chemistry teachers complained about the lack of LCD availability which makes it difficult for educators to display videos and teaching materials for students. And when chemistry learning activities take place, students lack attention and focus on the learning material, students can only focus for a few minutes and learning still tends to use learning media such as printed books. The use of printed books is less practical, so students tend to get bored and less motivated to learn and prefer to play on cell phones, where we know that Generation Z students are true technology users.

Generation Z students often have difficulty understanding more traditional learning concepts, such as reading books and taking notes. Students prefer to learn through videos, images, and direct interaction with digital technology (Stillman & Jonh, 2018). These obstacles require alternative solutions that can ease the task of educators and at the same time make students happy in participating in learning. One solution is to use the internet or by developing internet-based learning media, namely the *Learning Management System* (LMS).

A *Learning Management System* (LMS) is electronic software used to design, distribute, and create delivery formats for learning material that is being or will be implemented. LMS can be used by educators to function as a planning format in creating and managing learning materials to be taught and managing student activities, as well as managing daily grades, quizzes, final exams, and exams. Web-based LMS makes it easy for students to access it anytime and anywhere. One Learning Management System (LMS) that can be developed is *Moodle*. *Moodle* is a platform that was created and designed in such a way as a learning management system that was developed. *Moodle* can increase students' interest in learning so that students are more active in discussing the learning process (Putra, 2015).

Hydrocarbon material is one of the main materials in chemistry lessons that are dense in concepts and descriptions, so learning media is

needed that makes it easy for students to understand strong concepts during the learning process. Hydrocarbon material also contains the nomenclature of hydrocarbon compounds, which are numerous and varied, the structural formulas of hydrocarbon compounds, and the reactions that occur in hydrocarbon compounds. Through the Learning Management System (LMS) feature, educators can upload various formats of teaching materials that can be downloaded as well as a discussion feature that can be used to ask questions about material that is not yet understood, which can be accessed at any time, making it easier for educators to find out students' understanding. Khoiriyah (2019) states that *Moodle*-based Learning Management System (LMS) media influences learning outcomes and increases students' motivation in Hydrocarbon material.

Moodle, as a leading Learning Management System platform, offers flexibility that can be optimized to support the Problem-Based Learning model: Increased Student Involvement: The Problem-Based Learning model emphasizes active and participatory learning. *Moodle* can provide an environment that motivates students through interactive and collaborative features. Learning Flexibility: The Problem-Based Learning model requires adaptation to the unique learning needs of each student. *Moodle* allows for curriculum adjustments, material access, and assessment according to student characteristics and Ease of Collaboration: The Problem-Based Learning model requires team collaboration to solve problems. *Moodle* provides collaboration tools such as forums, discussion groups, and co-working spaces (Syamsuddin et al., 2022).

Research Methods

This research is a type of development research (Research and Development). The product developed is a Learning Management System (LMS) based on *Moodle* on the Problem-Based Learning Model.

The research design used in this research is based on the ADDIE development model which has several steps, namely:

The Analysis Stage aims to obtain information regarding problems or obstacles that arise in the implementation of learning and how to use learning media in the learning process. Results of observations and interviews conducted with chemistry subject teachers at SMAN 1 Tinambung. The Design Stage is carried out after the analysis stage is carried out, namely creating learning tools and creating a Moodle-based LMS design. Development Stage: The product is designed according to the design at the product design stage. The implementation stage is carried out to obtain responses from students and teachers regarding Moodle-based LMS products, finally, the evaluation stage is carried out at each stage in the development process to produce a product that is suitable for use in the learning process.

LMS Data Validity Analysis

The activities carried out in the validity data analysis process are interpreting the feasibility categories for each aspect and all aspects.

Table 1. Validity Categories of Five Learning Tool Development

Average Score	Validity Criteria
$3,5 \leq X/Y/Z \leq 4,0$	Very Valid
$3,0 \leq X/Y/Z < 3,5$	Valid
$2,5 \leq X/Y/Z < 3,0$	Fairly Valid
$1,5 \leq X/Y/Z < 2,5$	Less valid (revised)
$1,0 \leq X/Y/Z < 1,5$	Invalid (total revision)

Source: Widjoko, 2016.

Data Analysis on the Practicality of Media Learning

Data Observation Analysis of Device Implementation

Tabulate score data from learning observations by giving a score of 1 for 'yes' and 0 for 'no'. Then the percentage of implementation from the two observers was averaged. The results of this analysis can be explained in Table 2. Moodle-based LMS in the Problem-Based Learning

Model is said to be practical if the criteria reach moderate to very high.

Table 2. Learning Implementation Level Criteria

Level of Student Implementation	Criteria
81% - 100%	Very High
61% - 80%	High
41% - 60%	Medium
21% - 40%	Low
5% - 20%	Very Low

Source: Supriadi, 2015.

Analysis of Educator and Student Response Questionnaires

Data from the teacher and student response questionnaires were analyzed after knowing the practical value. The results of this analysis can be explained in Table 3.

Table 3. LMS Practicality Criteria

Level of Student Practicality	Criteria
75,01-100%	Very Practical
50,01-75,00%	Practical
25,01-50,00%	Not Practical
00-00,00%	Impractical

Source: Akbar, 2013.

Data Analysis of Learning Media Effectiveness

Data analysis of the effectiveness of learning media is seen from individual completion and the percentage of class completion. Individual completion scores are adjusted to the Minimum Completeness Criteria "*Kriteria Ketuntasan Minimal (KKM)*" standards set by the school, namely 78.

Results

Analysis Stage (Analysis)

The following is a description of the analysis obtained: In obtaining data and information from the performance analysis stage, the researcher carried out observations and interviews with the class XI MIA chemistry teacher at SMAN 1 Tinambung.

Based on the results of observations and interviews, during the learning process, the media used is still very limited. Teachers still rely on printed books and learning modules to provide material. Through needs analysis, the abilities or competencies that students need to learn to improve learning achievement can be determined. At this stage, three activities are carried out, namely curriculum analysis, analysis of student characteristics, and material analysis.

The LMS is designed to use technology as a form of adaptation for researchers to the characteristics of students who are already familiar with online learning due to education being affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. All students also have gadgets with adequate internet so that the products developed are fully usable by students.

Design Stage (Design)

- 1) Learning Tools creation
- 2) Moodle-based LMS design
- 3) Research Instrument creation

Development Stage (Development)

1) Creation of a Moodle-based LMS

- a. Create Moodle by setting up a domain
- b. If the domain is ready, then prepare hosting/cpanel
- c. Then register the domain in cpanel
- d. In cpanel search for software then select Softaculous Apps Installer
- e. On the Softaculous menu, look for Moodle then install it

f. After the installation is complete, Moodle is ready but the theme still has to be installed separately.

g. Next, the researchers created a new course called Hydrocarbons.

h. If Moodle is ready, continue with the theme installation process via Moodle.org.

i. Next, the researcher added a logo/image. When Moodle has been installed, several activities will be available. However, the

j. activities that are a combination of installing Moodle at the beginning do not include attendance activities. Therefore, researchers must install the presence plug-in via the official Moodle page, namely Moodle.org.

k. Next, researchers began to prepare the features that would be used. When several features that will be used by the LMS have been prepared.

l. The next step is to create and register student accounts for the courses that have been prepared.

The LMS that has been designed is then validated by media experts and material experts to determine its validity. Furthermore, the LMS is revised according to suggestions and input provided by validators.

2) Instrument Validation

Instrument validation is carried out to obtain information on the validity of the instrument to be used. The results obtained are declared valid with the following assessment:

Table 4. Media Expert Assessment Result

Assessment Aspect	Average Score	Category
Software Engineering	3.4	Very valid
Appearance	3.38	Very valid
Technical	3.22	Very valid
Average	3.33	Very valid

Table 5. Material Expert Assessment Results

Assessment Aspect	Average Score	Category
Contents	3.9	Very valid
Presentation	3.4	Very valid
Language Eligibility	3.87	Very valid
Average	3.72	Very valid

Table 6. Results of Instrument Validation Observation Sheet on Implementation of Media in Learning

Assessment Aspect	Average Score	Category
Observation Format	4	Very valid
Contents	3.5	Very valid
Language	3.75	Very valid
Average	3.75	Very valid

Table 7. Teacher Response Questionnaire Validation Results

Assessment Aspect	Average Score	Category
Observation Format	3.66	Very valid
Contents	3.83	Very valid
Language	3.66	Very valid
Contents	4	Very valid
Average	3.79	Very valid

Table 8. Student Response Questionnaire Validation Results

Assessment Aspect	Average Score	Category
Observation Format	3.83	Very valid
Contents	3.5	Very valid

Language	3.83	Very valid
Average	3.72	Very valid

Implementation Stage (Implementation)

1) Small scale trials

Small-scale trials were carried out after obtaining valid *Moodle*-based LMS media and supporting tools based on expert assessments.

In the implementation phase, a small-scale trial was first carried out on chemistry subject teachers and 12 students in class XII MIA. The trial was carried out during one meeting by providing hydrocarbon material via *Moodle*-based LMS using the Problem Based Learning model stages.

After the learning process was complete, students and chemistry teachers were given a questionnaire to see the response to the *Moodle*-based LMS media. Based on the research results, the responses of students and teachers in the field of chemistry to the media obtained data of 84.75% and 92.53%, this indicates that the practicality of *Moodle*-based LMS is in the very practical category.

After getting the results from small-scale trials, they were revised again until learning media was produced that was truly refined and ready to be used on research subjects.

2) Field trials

Practicality of a Moodle-based LMS

- Results of Learning Media Implementation Observation Sheet

Figure 1. Evaluation Value of Each Meeting

- Teacher questionnaire results

Table 9. Recapitulation of Teacher Response Results

Assessment Aspect	Percentage	Category
Navigation/Media Operations	91.67%	Very practical
Appearance	93.67%	Very practical
Benefit	92.18%	Very practical
Average	92.53%	Very practical

- Student questionnaire results

Table 10. Recapitulation of Student Response Results

Assessment Aspect	Percentage	Category
Display Design	90%	Very practical
Learning Design	80%	Very practical
Material	87%	Very practical
Implementability	83%	Very practical
Average	85%	Very practical

Effectiveness of Moodle-based LMS

The effectiveness of the *Moodle*-based LMS on the Hydrocarbon material being developed can be seen in the students' learning outcomes. The effectiveness assessment was carried out on 34 students of class XI MIA 3 SMAN 1 Tinambung. Apart from learning results, you can also see the results of student evaluations at each meeting held at the end of learning to determine students' understanding of the learning material. The average evaluation of each meeting can be seen in graphic Figure 2 below.

Furthermore, learning outcomes data is obtained from learning outcomes tests filled in by students after carrying out learning. Learning outcomes tests are carried out online via LMS. The results of the learning outcomes test can be seen in Table 13.

Figure 2. Evaluation Value of Each Meeting

Table 11. Results of Descriptive Analysis of Student Learning Outcome Tests

Variable	Descriptive Value
	XI MIA 3
Research subject	34
Ideal Value	100
KKM	78
Average	84.94
Maximum Score	100
Minimum Score	60
Number of Students Completed	29
Number of Students Who Did Not Complete	5
Class Completion Percentage	85.29%

In hydrocarbon material, 9 indicators of competency achievement are studied using *Moodle*-based LMS media in the Problem-Based Learning model. The percentage achievement of indicators of student learning outcomes can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Percentage Achievement Diagram for Each Indicator

Evaluation Stage

The evaluation stage in this research is applied at each stage of ADDIE. At this stage, it is carried out by revising the shortcomings of the *Moodle*-Based LMS that was developed if there are still deficiencies when implemented in the learning process, especially if there are input and suggestions that are taken into consideration in revising the *Moodle*-Based LMS.

Discussion

a. Validity

The validity of a *Moodle*-based LMS is obtained at the development stage. The following describes the validity of the instrument and the validity of the media based on the assessment of media experts and material experts.

Instrument Validity

The instruments used to measure the practicality of *Moodle*-based LMS are observation sheets on the implementation of learning media, teacher response questionnaires, and student response questionnaires which have been validated by the validator and declared valid in terms of format, content, and language which show that the questionnaire created is suitable for measuring practicality. product. Validation results can be seen in Table 6, 7, and 8.

Validity of Moodle Based LMS

Media Experts

Media expert assessment data was obtained from Engineering Education Lecturers at West

Sulawesi University. The assessment was carried out to determine the feasibility of a *Moodle*-based LMS through software engineering, appearance, and technical aspects. Based on the assessment results obtained, can be seen in Table 4.

Based on Table 4, the results of the *Moodle*-based LMS assessment by two media experts show that for the software engineering aspect, an average score of 3.4 was obtained in the very valid category. The *Moodle*-based LMS assessment from the appearance aspect by two media experts obtained an average score of 3.38 in the very valid category. From technical aspects, two media experts obtained an average score of 3.22 in the very valid category. Based on the validation results, it can be seen that the *Moodle*-based LMS developed can be used independently and is relatively easy to use for technological laypeople (Febaliza & Oktariani, 2020).

The assessment of these three aspects obtained an average score of 3.33 which, if converted based on the validity criteria table according to Widyoko (2016), means that the results of the validity assessment of the *Moodle*-based LMS being developed are the very valid category.

Material/ Content Experts

Material expert assessment data was obtained from UNM Chemistry Department Lecturers. Validation by material experts covers three aspects, namely learning design, material presentation, and language appropriateness. Based on Table 5, the results of the *Moodle*-based LMS assessment from the aspect of the

presentation of material content obtained an average score of 3.9, and the presentation aspect of material obtained an average score of 3.4. Meanwhile, the language appropriateness aspect obtained an average of 3.87 with very valid category. This shows that the material in the *Moodle*-based LMS has been presented coherently and has clear sources. So, it makes it easier for students to understand the hydrocarbon material presented.

The average score for all aspects of the assessment from chemistry learning experts is 3.72, which if converted based on the validity criteria table according to Widyoko (2016), means that the results of the *Moodle*-based LMS assessment are in the very valid category.

Practicality of Moodle Based LMS

The practicality of the *Moodle*-Based LMS was assessed from the observation sheet on the implementation of the *Moodle*-Based LMS as well as the teacher and student response questionnaire. The *Moodle*-based LMS that was developed was applied in the learning process using the Problem-Based Learning model.

Learning with Problem-Based Learning begins with a problem orientation phase by focusing students' attention, the teacher displays phenomena or problems that express everyday problems related to hydrocarbon material.

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Next is the phase of organizing students. The teacher organizes students to analyze the problems given. At this stage, students also identify what is known and ask about the problem orientation that has been given and write down any information related to the problem. At this stage, students identify what is known and write down any information related to the problem. Both phases obtained an average of 81.25% and 100%. Students can write down key information from existing problems, able to analyze questions.

The next stage is guiding the investigation. Teachers provide direction and opportunities to students. Students collect available information on hydrocarbons and conduct literature studies from various relevant sources. The stage of preparing a problem-solving plan shows that students already have the ability to write down answers and discuss other possible answers. The percentage of achievement at this stage reaches 100%, meaning that students' ability to check the suitability of the problem by compiling answers is very good.

The next stage is developing and presenting the results. The percentage of achievement of this syntax is 100%. Next, the final stage is evaluating and analyzing the results of problem-solving, namely, students write down the results of observations or the results of analysis of problem-solving that have been presented by each group. At this stage, students are invited to draw conclusions based on their language. The percentage at this stage is 100%.

An observer's assessment of the implementation of a *Moodle*-based LMS is needed to determine the feasibility of the product being developed. This is shown by all learning steps having an implementation level of 96.35% in the very high category.

The next practicality assessment, namely the teacher response questionnaire and student response questionnaire, shows that the *Moodle*-based LMS developed is very practical to use in the learning process.

Based on the student responses in Table 8, the display design aspect obtained from student responses was 90%, the learning design aspect from students obtained a percentage of 80%, the material aspect 87% which was in the very practical category. This shows that the developed *Moodle*-based LMS makes it easier for students to learn.

The percentage of responses to media implementation aspects obtained from students as shown by the results of the student response questionnaire was 83% which was in the very practical category.

Next, the teacher response results which can be seen in Table 7 in the media navigation/operation aspect, the results of the teacher response questionnaire obtained a percentage of 91.67%, and the display aspect was 93.67%. The media benefits aspect in the results of the teacher response questionnaire obtained a percentage of 92.18% in the very practical category. This shows that the developed *Moodle*-based LMS provides benefits for students and teachers in the learning process.

The results of the analysis of the *Moodle*-based LMS implementation observation questionnaire as well as the teacher and student response questionnaires overall gave a positive response to the product, so it can be concluded that the *Moodle*-based LMS developed was declared feasible in terms of practicality (Yusuf et al., 2016).

The *Moodle*-based LMS developed has many advantages, including having an attractive appearance, easy to access on laptops and smartphones, easy to operate, economical in nature, and equipped with audio-visual media which makes it easy for students to learn independently.

Effectiveness of Moodle-Based LMS

Effectiveness aspect testing was carried out to determine the effect of implementing a *Moodle*-based LMS in the learning process using the Problem-Based Learning model on student learning outcomes.

At the first meeting, the average evaluation result was 97.64. The indicators taught at the first meeting were identifying hydrocarbon compounds in everyday life, indicators explaining the characteristics of carbon atoms, and indicators analyzing types of C atoms based on the number of C atoms bound to the chain of carbon atoms. (primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary C atoms). Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that the completeness of each indicator was 77%, 97%, and 90%, respectively. It can be concluded that at the first meeting, there was one incomplete indicator, this occurred because students still lacked understanding of how to identify a hydrocarbon

compound, and students were not yet accustomed to using *Moodle* LMS media with a learning model.

The evaluation results at the second meeting obtained an average evaluation result of 97.14 and the percentage results for each indicator at the second meeting, namely the indicator for determining hydrocarbon compounds based on the bonds contained in the carbon chain was 83.3% (complete), the indicator for determining the general formula of alkanes, alkenes, and alkynes based on the molecular formula 76.57% (incomplete), the indicators explain the nomenclature of alkene compounds, and alkyne based on IUPAC rules 81%, from these results it turns out that there has been no increase, there are still incomplete indicators. There are still some students who are not used to using LMS media, so they do not watch learning videos properly.

At the third and fourth meetings, there was an increase in the evaluation results, namely 97.67 and 97.90, and completeness was obtained for each indicator at the meeting, namely indicators predicting isomer types 86.4%, indicators analyzing the physical properties of hydrocarbon compounds 84% and indicators analyzing reactions -simple reaction of 84% hydrocarbon compounds. This happens because students are used to using a *Moodle*-based LMS by watching and re-reading the learning material available on the LMS before learning begins.

The effectiveness of the *Moodle*-based LMS developed can be seen from student learning outcomes tests which function to determine students' cognitive level regarding the hydrocarbon material being taught. The media developed is declared effective if class completion reaches 80% based on the KKM applicable at the school, namely 78.

The results obtained from the student learning outcomes test showed that 29 students completed, and 5 students did not complete with a class completion percentage of 85.29% and individual determination which showed that the media developed was effectively used in the learning process, so it can be concluded that the use of LMS is based on *Moodle* in the learning

process effectively improves student learning outcomes (Pratama, 2020).

Conclusion

The research and development of Moodle-based LMS that has been carried out can be concluded as follows: Moodle-based LMS meets the criteria for being suitable for use. This feasibility is based on the validity value of media experts and material experts who state that the Moodle-based LMS is very valid, practicality is obtained based on the observation sheet of the implementation of learning media, teacher and student response questionnaires state that the Moodle-based LMS is very practical in its use and product effectiveness is obtained from learning outcome tests. students who stated that the Moodle-based LMS met the criteria for being effective for use.

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